

Whose and What Aid Securitization? An Analysis of EU aid narratives and flows¹

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Abstract

There is a growing perception that arguments favouring security are gaining ground in the aid narrative and that aid allocation is changing accordingly. This work explores the extent and features of such shifts in the particular case of the EU.

We observe the evolution of development paradigms (social development, sustainable development, and security) and aid motives (solidarity, common interests, and self-interest) in the aid discourse. This is done by means of content analysis of strategic aid documents of a selection of European donors (the EU institutions, the Netherlands, the UK, Germany, France, Sweden and Spain). We then explore the eventual shift in the aid budgets of those same donors.

In line with previous work on EU aid securitization, we find evidence of securitization in both narratives and aid flows. However, such trend is far from homogeneous, showing the complexity and diversity within the Union. There is practically no evidence of securitization in the EU institutions, Spain and Sweden. We find mixed evidence for the Netherlands, Germany and France (where narratives and flow changes towards securitization do not necessarily match) and, finally, a significant shift in the UK, where aid narratives and aid flows have been significantly securitized.

Keywords: aid; development; security; securitization; European Union

Introduction

The securitization of aid could be defined as a process where targets such as security and stability (in partner but also in donor countries) crowd out human and sustainable development goals (poverty reduction, gender equality, climate action, etc.). The debate around aid securitization has renewed in the 2010s as a result of the Great Recession that hit Europe in the late 2000s, the conflicts in the Middle East, the subsequent flows of migrants and refugees crossing (or trying to cross) the Mediterranean, and rising populist and nationalist movements and parties (Miles, 2012, Brown et al., 2016). Similarly to what happened after the 9/11 terrorist attacks with US international assistance, the ‘aid sector’ as well as several scholars are now pointing towards a process of securitization of the aid channelled by European donors. This could be manifested, for instance, and according to the charity sector, in rising aid budgets sustained by increasing domestic refugee costs oriented to dealing with immigrants and refugees, and the crowding-out of the development assistance that effectively crosses the border to be spent in partner countries.

Building on previous studies on this same topic,³ this article explores the eventual process of securitization of European Union (EU) aid at two levels: narratives and flows. The case of the EU is relevant for a number of reasons. Firstly, the EU is the world’s largest donor. According to OECD figures for 2019 (hence, before the materialization of Brexit), the EU institutions and the 28 member states (MS) deliver over half of the total traditional aid. Secondly, this volume of disbursement somehow mirrors its political role in the promotion of development cooperation matters in the aid community. Thirdly, when compared to other Development Assistance

Committee (DAC) donors, the EU is (or has been) seen as a particularly constructivist donor, aimed at alleviating world poverty and building regional and global governance structures.

This article is structured as follows. The first section accounts for previous studies on aid securitization. It also advances some methodological issues that are more deeply addressed in the second section. In the latter, (i) we define ‘which’ Europe is being analysed. We explore the main donors -EU institutions, Germany, the United Kingdom (UK), France, the Netherlands, Sweden and Spain. (ii) We also describe the methodology for our discourse analysis -the criteria for selecting official documents and the definitions of development paradigms and aid motives- and (iii) for the aid flows’ assessment in terms of securitization. The third section discusses the evidence of securitization found in aid narratives. The fourth section deals with securitization in aid flows and the last section concludes.

Theoretical framework: aid securitization in academic literature

One of the rationales behind aid securitization is the security-development nexus (see, for instance, Faust and Messner (2005), Keukeleire and Raube (2013), Khoo (2019) and Larzillière (2019)). From this perspective, security is a pre-condition for development. Also, development leads to security. If this assumption is accepted, it is only natural that aid and security policies end up being interlinked. Critics of this approach are not reluctant to accept the link between the security and development spheres. However, they point out that the political interlinkage can result in a crowding out of development objectives in aid policies, which can turn into objectives more clearly aligned with donors’ interests such as security goals (Faust and Messner, 2005). This is the reason why aid securitization has been generally addressed critically by activists, experts and academia.

The concept of securitization can be traced back to the Copenhagen School. Seminal works by Barry Buzan, Ole Wæver and Jaap de Wilde led to a body of literature devoted to the theoretical and empirical study of how certain political domains (including international relations) transit from the political to the security agenda. “Something acquires a security status as a result of an intersubjective process involving a securitization actor and an audience” (Balzacq and Guzzini, 2015). That is, “when a securitizing actor uses a rhetoric of existential threat and thereby takes an issue out of what under those conditions is ‘normal politics’, we have a case of securitization” (Buzan et al., 1997). In other words, “securitization refers to the process through which an issue is labelled a ‘security’ issue by an (elite) actor, a process which moves the issue out of the normal political sphere and into the security sphere” (Nyman, 2013). Therefore, according to securitization theory, security is a (illocutionary) speech act, that solely by uttering ‘security’ turns something into an actual security issue (Taureck, 2006). In the case of this study, applied to development cooperation policies in the EU, securitization implies the subordination of EU development policy to security objectives (Bergmann, 2017).

Securitization theory contains a useful analytical framework for exploring whether EU aid has gone through a securitization process. The main elements of the framework are the following (Nyman, 2013, Balzacq et al., 2016). (1) Elites. Securitization is issued by an elite actor, usually States. In our case, these elite actors are States or communities of States and multilateral institutions issuing the aid narrative through white books. (2) Referent subjects. These are, in our study, donor countries’ societies, that are meant to become or feel safer as a result of aid policies. (3) The audience in the securitization process, an element linked to the previous one. Although this particular issue goes beyond the scope of our study, it points out an interesting element

which is whether securitized aid discourses are specifically directed to ‘non-convinced’ audiences in public opinions and/or to political parties. In relation to this, (4) another element of the framework is the ‘why’ - why would elite actors securitize, instead of politicize, a given political domain -. According to Nyman (2013), this would be done with the intention of giving such domain (aid, in our case) extra priority, leading to an increased public profile and/or budget. This would eventually make sense in a (5) context (the conditions historically associated with the threat) when, after the Great Recession and the so-called migration crisis, aid policies might be crowded-out by domestic economic and social needs in the European context. Lastly, (6) referent objects. In the aid political domain, there are several referent objects (previously identified by academic literature) that might eventually be securitized: energy and the environment, global health, trafficking, identity and migration, religion or cyber-security. As shown later in this article, a great deal of them actually appear as key topics in the white papers explored (Nyman, 2013, Balzacq et al., 2016).

In spite of its explanatory potential, securitization theory has been criticized for a number of reasons. Firstly, for not being critical enough or for being morally ambivalent and, in relation to this, for not having a clear normative agenda. Secondly, for being ambiguous as to how it refers to the speech act: the speech act is sometimes defined as intersubjective (implying crossed messages between the elite actor and its audience) or, alternatively and more frequently, as a single utterance. A third critique is, therefore, that the audience remains under-studied in securitization analytical frameworks. Fourthly, securitization theory has also been criticized for sticking to the study of the speech, despite the fact that securitization can happen in other political elements, such as institutions or budgets. Fifthly, securitization theory proves useful for ‘tracking’ securitization processes but not for testing causal links between securitization and additional phenomena (Nyman, 2013, Williams, 2003).

It could be argued, however, that despite these criticisms, securitization theory still operates as a valid framework for our study. In relation to the first critique, our aim is, precisely, to track signals of securitization in EU aid from a positivist, rather than a normative viewpoint. Regardless of the importance of the audience, we here assume the speech act to be a single utterance (stated in aid white papers). Moreover, since our aim is to ‘track’ an eventual securitization process, the limitations of this theory for testing causal links is not a major issue. We also deal with the somehow narrower view of sticking to the analysis of the narrative by incorporating a study of aid flows too, in line with previous studies on aid securitization.

Indeed, according to academic literature on aid securitization, evidence of this process can be found in three distinct (but complementary) levels: aid discourse, allocations and institutions (Brown et al., 2016, Furness and Gänzle, 2016). The securitization of the aid discourse is manifested in increasing references to security, conflict, fragile states, terrorism or the perils of migration in development cooperation white papers, master plans or official interventions in national parliaments or multilateral fora. Aid securitization can also be shown in rising aid funds allocated to sectors and projects aimed at improving peace and security or at dealing with migration - the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa could be an example of the latter. Lastly, securitization can be revealed in the aid institutional architecture through the creation of administrative levels, units or tools aimed at coping with development cooperation and security issues simultaneously. For instance, Bergmann (2018) claims that the EU Instrument contributing to Stability and Peace (IcSP) is a manifestation of a securitization of EU institutions.

Previous studies on the securitization of EU aid track this pattern at the three levels mentioned above. For instance, work by Furness and Gänzle (2016) and by Brown, Grävingholt, and Raddatz (2016) explore it via (1) the aid discourse, (2) the institutional setting and (3) aid allocation. Keukeleire and Raube (2013) propose an alternative categorization that includes (1) the discourse, (2) policy instruments, (3) policy action and (4) institutional frameworks. All of these studies conclude that the aid-security nexus is increasingly present in the EU narrative. On their part, Orbie and Del Biondo (2015), who focus on EU aid to Chad, conclude that, although democratic governance tools of the EU are indeed contaminated by security concerns, development cooperation and humanitarian aid appear not to be.

In all of these cases, the methodology is based on the authors' summaries and interpretations of official documents, bolstered by semi-structured interviews. However, Petrikova and Lazell (2017) take a different approach to studying multilateral donors such as the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the European Commission, and the World Bank. Their study of these agents' discourse consists of codifying official texts such as the World Bank's World Development Reports.

Previous studies on this topic find evidence of securitization. However, several questions remain unanswered, and some debates remain open. Firstly, when studying the EU, most of the work sticks to the Union itself: EU institutions, policy tools, narratives or aid flows (Furness and Gänzle, 2016, Keukeleire and Raube, 2013, Orbie and Del Biondo, 2015). Given the complexity of the EU as a global actor, including other relevant MS, such as France, Germany, the Netherlands, Spain, Sweden and the UK, can draw a more detailed picture of the eventual securitization of EU aid. In this sense, although Brown *et al.* (2016) explore additional MS (France and the UK), increasingly relevant players, such as Germany, are not included in the sample. Moreover, in this case, countries are not explored with the exact same standardized technique, making results not entirely comparable between countries and across time. Thirdly, aid flows are explored from the geographical viewpoint (Furness and Gänzle, 2016). Although this might show signs of securitization, a sector approach, specifically targeting aid with security goals, might provide useful complementary information.

In this work, with a similar standardised technique to that of Petrikova and Lazell (2017), we codify the aid discourse of major EU donors (accounting for over three quarters of total EU aid) in the early 2000s and the mid 2010s. This allows us to observe the gradual securitization of aid narratives across time and also to explore the extent to which such securitization is the result of a changing narrative in the Union as a whole or in some of its members. By doing this, this work aims to widen the scope of the study of the EU as a global actor (going beyond EU institutions) and therefore to nuance the results found by previous studies. Also, by exploring strategic documents at two different moments in time, the evolution of the variable at work is better seized. Finally, by studying the sector allocation of EU aid, we attempt to offer a complementary picture of the specific goals of aid, regardless of its geographical allocation.

Methodology: how to assess securitization in aid discourses and flows?

First of all, who or what is Europe as a donor?

EU development cooperation is the result of MS' bilateral programmes as well as contributions to EU institutions and non-EU multilateral programmes that are channelled towards third countries as Official Development Assistance (ODA). Therefore, it could be argued that the EU aid narrative is that of the 28 MS plus that of the EU institutions.⁴

These are donors of very different sizes. ‘Big’ donors are larger countries delivering higher volumes of ODA. It could be argued that, as a result of their economic and demographic size, their capacity to shape the global development system and the discourse and behaviour of EU institutions is also stronger. However, in collective action dynamics, smaller players can systematically punch above their weight, as shown, in the case of the EU, by ECFR’s scorecards’ results in relation to Lithuania or Poland (ECFR, 2016). Nevertheless, when it comes to EU aid, the leadership of big players, such as the UK, has been documented (Olivié and Pérez, 2017). Therefore, analysing the discourse of a selection of relevant donors might result in a fairly precise idea of where EU aid is headed overall.

According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) figures, the top eight EU donors by volume of disbursement throughout the 2000–2019 period were Germany, the UK, the EU institutions, France, the Netherlands, Sweden, Italy, and Spain.⁵ These donors account for almost 88% of the total ODA channelled from EU countries plus the EU institutions in this period. Therefore, there is a strong concentration of aid in a small number of donors. Thus, it could be said that the analysis of these countries’ and institutions’ discourses might give us a good sense of the prevailing European narrative of international assistance.

Moreover, a great deal of these donors (with the exceptions of Italy and Spain) are financially committed to aid policy, meaning that their relative effort is near the global target of reaching 0.7% of their GNI. A country’s high aid disbursements might relate to that country’s economic size; not necessarily meaning that such aid volume represents a large share of the donors’ public budget or GDP. Take, for instance, the US, which tops the traditional donors’ ranking in aid volume (34.61 billion US dollars in 2019, according to OECD figures), but whose aid budget is only at 0.16% of its Gross National Income (GNI). This is not, however, the case for Germany, the UK, France, the Netherlands, or Sweden, all of which support aid budgets that are above the OECD Development Assistance Committee (DAC) average in relation to the sizes of their economies. However, Italy and Spain, on their part, are well below the average. Their aid budgets stand at 0.24% and 0.21% of their GNI, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1. ODA budgets of major EU MS donors

	ODA in volume (total, 2000-2019 period, in millions of current US dollars)	ODA as % of GNI (in 2019)
Germany	276,816	0.60
UK	255,451	0.70
EU institutions	249,761	-
France	198,253	0.44
Netherlands	103,822	0.59
Sweden	87,720	0.99
Italy	72,818	0.24
Spain	64,329	0.21
Other DAC EU donors	187,216	
Total EU + EU institutions	1,496,187	
DAC average		0.38

Source: OECD DAC2a (Data extracted on 23 February 2021) and authors’ calculations.

We can thus assume that these donors' narratives and flows are a fair representation of the EU narratives and flows of international assistance. Moreover, with the exceptions of Italy and Spain, they are committed donors, indicating that aid is a non-negligible aspect of domestic politics in these countries. We can therefore further assume that their aid narratives represent important communication tools with their own domestic societies.

Which narratives should we be analysing?

As in previous studies on this same topic, aid narratives are explored in political and official documents; more precisely, in the key strategic and/or planning documents of international development cooperation. This requires identifying which official documents encapsulate the strategic objectives, development paradigms and motives for aid on the part of different donors.

Such identification can be conducted via the DAC peer review, a mechanism established by the OECD. Periodically, a given DAC donor is evaluated by two peers from the same group. The evaluation issued by the OECD at the end of the process includes, among other information and conclusions, references to the key strategic documents guiding the evaluated donor's aid policy. The main advantage of this identification technique is that it is the reviewed donor who identifies what it considers to be its key strategic document on aid, making sure that we are observing its core messages regarding development cooperation. It could be argued that, since peer reviews are not conducted on a yearly basis, we might be missing some important official documents to be explored (that would be published in between peer reviews). However, this risk is minimized by the fact that these documents are multiannual by nature and, in some cases, might even be in force throughout two distinct peer-reviews, as it is the case, for instance, with the European Commission and the first consensus on development (the framework for both the 2007 and the 2012 evaluations).⁶ Whenever possible, OECD information was triangulated with public information provided by the donor, as was the case for Spain, where the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, European Union and Cooperation identifies its main strategic documents,⁷ and for the EU.⁸ In the case of France, which lacks a multiyear strategic document guiding aid policy, local experts were contacted in order to identify the two most relevant publications for this study.

As already mentioned, our intention is to explore the extent to which the aid discourse has evolved as a result of the recent economic crisis and the ongoing so-called refugee and migrant crises. These two historical events constitute the elements of the 'context', following the Copenhagen School's analytical framework. With this goal in mind, it is necessary, for each donor, to select two strategic documents: one pre-dating the events that conform the context and another from the post-crisis period. For this very reason, Italy had to be excluded from the sample, as it was not possible to identify a publicly available document reflecting the country's aid strategy in the early 2000s. It should be noted, however, that the seven remaining donors account for almost 83% of total MS aid, plus that of the EU institutions, in US current dollars and cumulated throughout the 2000-2019 period, according to OECD figures.

We decided to observe the gradual evolution towards aid securitization starting in the early 2000s. By doing this, the 'pre-context' period coincides with the adoption of the Millennium Declaration in 2000 and the subsequent approval of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs); an agenda that implied an important boost for aid policies and multilateralism. The 'post-context' period occurs after the Great Recession (and its long-lasting effects) as well as the so-called migration crisis. Although the financial crisis erupted in the United States in late 2008, the impact on the European countries observed in this study was shown from 2009 onwards.

While Germany, the UK and France all recorded negative economic growth in 2009 and slow growth until 2012, according to World Bank data, the Netherlands, Spain and Sweden went through an economic recession between 2009 and 2013. As for the so-called refugee crisis, this was largely the consequence of the eruption of conflicts in the Mediterranean area (namely Syria). Refugee inflows increased in 2014, peaked in 2015, and then strongly decreased in the following years. In short, the ‘context’ is made up of historical events that can be dated between 2009 and 2015.

As for the strategic documents referring to the ‘pre-context’, all of them were published between 2000 and 2003, with the exception of the first European Consensus, launched in 2006. Since, as pointed out above, these are strategic multi-year documents that are not renewed annually, the three-year lapse for most documents is explained. In the case of the EU, no strategic documents of that nature were published before the first Consensus. However, as it was published a couple of years before the eruption of the crisis, it still seizes the essence of the 2000s narrative on aid. Also, although MDGs were only formally adopted in 2001, Spanish, British and German strategic documents are still valid for the analysis of that ‘pre-context’ period, since they include a discourse that can be traced back to the 1990s social summits and therefore had been in the making before its official adoption.

A similar logic applies to the ‘post-context’ period. Firstly, all documents are multiannual strategic texts published between 2013 and 2018; that is, at the end of or immediately after the ‘context’ period (2009-2015). Secondly, their multi-year nature and the fact that planification cycles vary from one country to another prevent the possibility of only selecting documents published in the same year. Thirdly, despite the fact that some of these documents were published before the formal adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015, that agenda was already being shaped in the first half of the 2010s and therefore its discourse could be seized in strategic documents published between 2013 and 2015 by Dutch, German, Swedish or British authorities.

Table 2. Key EU aid strategic documents

EU	European Consensus on Development (EC, 2006).
	European New Consensus on Development (EC, 2017).
France	<i>Comité Interministériel de la Coopération Internationale et du Développement (CICID). Relevé de conclusions</i> , 2018 (CICID, 2018).
	<i>Relevé de conclusions du Comité Interministériel de la Coopération Internationale et du développement (CICID)</i> , 2002 (CICID, 2002).
Germany	Charter for the Future – One World, Our Responsibility, Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2014 (FMECD, 2014).
	Poverty Reduction – a Global Responsibility. Program of Action 2015, The German Government's Contribution toward Halving Extreme Poverty Worldwide, Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2001 (FMECD, 2001).
Italy	International Development Cooperation. Three-year Programming and Policy Planning Document 2017-2019, 2016 (Repubblica-italiana, 2016).
Netherlands	A World to Gain: A New Agenda for Aid, Trade and Investment, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Netherlands, 2013 (MFA, 2013).

	Mutual Interests, Mutual Responsibilities Dutch Development Cooperation en Route to 2015, Directorate-General for International Cooperation, 2003 (DGIC, 2003).
Spain	<i>V Plan Director de la Cooperación Española 2018-2021</i> , 2018 (SECIPI, 2018).
	<i>I Plan Director de la Cooperación Española 2001-2004</i> , 2000 (SECIPI, 2000).
Sweden	Government Communication. Policy framework for Swedish development cooperation and humanitarian assistance, 2016 (Government-of-Sweden, 2016).
	Cooperation and humanitarian assistance. Government Bill. Shared Responsibility: Sweden’s Policy for Global Development, 2002 (Government-of-Sweden, 2002).(i)
UK	UK Aid: Tackling Global Challenges in the National Interest, HM Treasury, Department for International Development, 2015 (HM-Treasury and DFID, 2015).
	Eliminating World Poverty: Making Globalisation Work for the Poor. White Paper on International Development, Department for International Development, 2000 (DFID, 2000).

(i) Despite its title, as noticed by Swedish authorities, this document is not a legal bill per se. Therefore, it has a similar nature to other planning and white papers selected for this study.

Source: Authors’ elaboration.

As for EU institutions, although the consensus on development are meant to be the EU’s overall strategic approach to development, and are the result of the very different approaches of all MS and the EU institutions, those are the only white papers with the direct intervention of the EU development institutions, reflecting, to a great extent, their approach to foreign aid.

Similarly to Petrikova and Lazell (2017)’s work, these 14 texts were coded, seeking evidence of different development paradigms. Therefore, a decision was made as to what could be the prevailing paradigms (including the security approach) and how to define them. It could be argued that the early 2000s were characterized by the social development paradigm summarised in the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) approved in 2001, in force until 2015, and echoed in the national development cooperation strategies of the early 2000s. Such paradigm might have evolved into its ‘natural successor’, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) agenda, approved in 2015; or, else, into a security agenda, according to previous studies on this topic. It is therefore necessary to establish a series of codes corresponding to each of these three paradigms (Table 3).

Table 3. Paradigms of development and families of codes

1	Social development agenda or paradigm	2	Sustainable development agenda or paradigm	3	Security agenda or paradigm
1.1	Poverty / Poverty eradication	2.1	Economic development / Job creation / Decent work	3.1	Terrorism / Counter-terrorism / Radicalisation
1.2	Hunger / Food security / Malnutrition	2.2	Political rights / Human rights / Governance	3.2	Migration / Border control / Mobility / Refugees / Displacements
1.3	Gender	2.3	Environmental sustainability / Climate change	3.3	Failed or fragile states or countries

1.4 Education	2.4 Equity / Inequality	3.4 Conflict / Conflict prevention / Post-conflict intervention
1.5 Health		3.5 Stability / Instability

Source: Authors' elaboration.

It can be said that some objectives and goals belong to more than one agenda. For instance, the fight against hunger was part of the MDGs (paradigm 1), but is also included in the SDGs (paradigm 2). Likewise, peace can be considered an aspect of security (paradigm 3), but it is also SDG number 16 (paradigm 2). By establishing families of codes, our aim is to seize the key ideas and spirit that define them. The MDGs were largely an agenda of social development (1), where donors were expected to focus on poverty (1.1), hunger (1.2), gender (1.3), education (1.4), and health (1.5). Although the MDGs also included environmental targets, it was not until the approval of the SDGs that the environmental and climate change agenda (2.3) became an essential part (perhaps the most important) of the global development agenda.

Unlike the MDGs, this paradigm of sustainable development (2) is also characterised by the fact that it acknowledges the complex nature of development processes, which is not limited to their social facet. The social dimension of development goes hand in hand, necessarily, with economic development – interpreted in this paradigm as a process of sustained and sustainable development leading to the creation of decent work (2.1) – and with political development (2.2). The SDGs are also recognised for their emphasis on inequality (2.4) (Sachs, 2012, Le Blanc, 2015).

Lastly, as regards the security paradigm (3), this assembles certain key concepts previously defined by the academic literature reviewed above: concepts of terrorism and radicalisation (3.1), migrations and refugees (3.2), failed or fragile states (3.3), conflicts and their prevention (3.4), and stability (3.5) (Orbie and Del Biondo, 2015, Brown et al., 2016, Furness and Gänzle, 2016).⁹

Apart from the general objectives or paradigms of development, donors' strategic texts generally indicate motives for aid that could be somehow linked to either altruistic or selfish sets of motives.

In this sense, the paradigm of social development responds, in general terms, to a North-South logic where donors (usually in the Global North) have a moral responsibility, a legal obligation, and/or a feeling of solidarity towards the Global South (code 4: solidarity / moral obligation / responsibility). This North-South logic is broken (or at least reshaped) in the sustainable development paradigm, which places a stronger emphasis on global public goods (such as climate) and, therefore, on the need for collective action and efforts that lead to the fulfilment of common interests (code 5: common goods / common efforts / common interests / global public goods). As for the security paradigm, it operates under a North-South logic (similar to the social development paradigm), where international relations should aim at protecting national interests (code 6: self-help / self-interest / national interest).

Although certain motives tend to be connected to certain paradigms, they are not necessarily bound to one another (as we shall see in the particular case of the Netherlands). As a result, we have set distinct codes for these three motives that will be analysed separately in the following section.

These 14 strategic documents were hand-coded by one of the authors, using the application Atlas.ti. Hand-coding proved to be more consistent than other automatized techniques due to the

wide variety of wordings for the same issues (specific paradigms or motives). Consistency and inter-coder reliability are guaranteed since all documents were also independently coded by a research assistant. Discrepancies between these two coding processes were then explored and processed.

In each document, the paragraphs coded were only those that refer to the objectives and/or to the motives of aid, meaning that in most cases, only some sections of the strategic documents were coded. For instance, the most recent white paper published by the Netherlands' authorities sets the strategic objectives for aid but also for trade and for investment. As a result, although the document is 74 pages long, only 74 paragraphs were coded. Such paragraphs are located in the summary, the introduction, and section 3 on "changing relationships" (excluding "trade relationships" in section 3.5). In general terms, sections on policy coherence for development (which are part of most of the documents explored) were excluded as these refer, precisely, to the actions to be undertaken in political fields different to aid, to achieve global development objectives. Also, any text referring to other aspects of aid policy, such as tools or budgets, was left uncoded since our research is focusing on the objectives and motives of aid (Table 4).

Texts have been coded following development paradigms (Table 3), as well as motives of aid (codes 4–6). As a result, 1,483 paragraphs were labelled. Because one paragraph or quote can be labelled with more than one code referring to objectives, to motives, or to both, this resulted in 4,340 assigned labels (4,139 on paradigms and 201 on motives).

Table 4. Coded text in strategic documents

Strategic document	Paragraphs coded (Nr.)	Objectives (Nr. references)	Motives (Nr. references)
EU 1	56	168	6
EU 2	74	313	5
France 1	10	29	4
France 2	45	87	3
Germany 1	208	565	7
Germany 2	73	259	12
Netherlands 1	58	153	10
Netherlands 2	74	236	27
Spain 1	133	201	16
Spain 2	148	418	17
Sweden 1	133	402	30
Sweden 2	153	561	5
UK 1	192	466	19
UK 2	126	281	40
Total	1,483	4,139	201

Source: Authors' elaboration.

How to deal with the securitization of aid flows?

Tracking the securitization of aid flows can be done through aid sector allocation as reported in the Creditor Reporting System (CRS); an OECD database on all DAC members' (including EU institutions') bilateral commitments that provides an activity breakdown along with some description. Such dataset includes the 'conflict, peace and security' sector (code 152), under the macro-sector I 'social sectors'. This database allows for the identification of one of the policy developments most often referred to when denouncing the securitization of EU aid, which is the

EU Emergency Trust Fund for Stability and Addressing Root Causes of Irregular Migration and Displaced Persons in Africa established at the Valletta Summit in 2015.

Aid channelled by the EU institutions and MS through this fund is often allocated to sector 430 ('other, multisector'). From a thematic standpoint, the EU Trust Fund projects can indeed range from security sector reform to water and sanitation, when providing funds to this extra-budgetary instrument. However, this is not known beforehand. For this reason, the *ex-ante* sector allocation of the Trust Fund declared by the EU and its MS to the OECD-DAC has been adjusted according to the annual reports issued by the European Commission. These reports informed that 53% of the Fund's actual expenditure targeted security projects, while the CRS only acknowledged 32%. The adjustment is summarized in table 5, while a list of the aid activities reported by EU donors in the period under analysis is provided in the annex along with their *ex-ante* sectoral allocation.

Table 5. Sector reallocation of the Africa Trust Fund expenditure.

	CRS original (millions 2018 US dollars)			Background memory (current millions Euro)		CRS redistributed (millions 2018 US dollars)		
	2016	2017		Cumulated June 2019	2016	2017		
Security	-	159.50	32%	2,024	53%	97	165	53%
Others	183.50	151.90	68%	1,839	47%	86	146	47%
Total	183.50	311.40		3,863		183.50	311.40	

Source: OECD CRS (Data extracted on 10 Mar 2021), EU (2019) and authors' calculations.

Is the securitization of the narrative of EU aid a reality?

Given the different formats and structures of these 14 texts, the number of quotes per document varies greatly: from a maximum of 208 coded paragraphs (in Germany's document for the earlier period) to only 10 quotes in France's document for that same period (Table 6). Here again, the results are analysed as a proportion of assigned labels per document. For instance, in the case of the Netherlands, 58 paragraphs were labelled with paradigm codes in its strategic document from the first period. As different objectives can coexist within one paradigm, as well as in different paradigms, several paragraphs were labelled with more than one code. Therefore, the earlier Netherlands document includes 153 references to development paradigms scattered across its 58 paragraphs: of these, 63 refer to the social development paradigm, 54 to the sustainable development paradigm, and 36 to the security paradigm.

Table 6. Development paradigms in EU MS discourses (quotes by code, % of total coded text)

	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)	(E)	(F)	(G)	(H)
	Social development paradigm	Nr. of codes	Sustainable development paradigm	Nr. of codes	Security paradigm	Nr. of codes	Total Nr. of codes	Nr. of paragraphs
1st period								
EU inst.	45.2	76	41.1	69	13.7	23	168	56
Netherlands	41.2	63	35.3	54	23.5	36	153	58
UK	42.9	200	44.8	209	12.2	57	466	192
Germany	45.8	259	44.4	251	9.7	57	565	208
France	51.7	15	48.3	14	0.0	0	29	10
Sweden	39.6	159	47.5	191	12.9	52	402	133

Spain	69.2	139	22.4	45	8.4	17	201	57
Average	47.2		41.1		11.7		-	-
Total							1,729	658
							Total	
2nd period	Social development paradigm	Number of codes	Sustainable development paradigm	Number of codes	Security paradigm	Number of codes	Number of codes	Number of paragraphs
EU inst.	26.8	84	57.8	181	15.3	48	313	74
Netherlands	38.6	91	38.1	90	23.3	55	236	74
UK	41.6	117	23.5	66	34.9	98	281	126
Germany	32.0	83	51.4	133	16.6	43	259	73
France	40.2	35	41.4	36	18.4	16	87	45
Sweden	34.6	194	49.9	280	15.5	87	561	153
Spain	29.7	124	55.7	233	14.6	61	418	148
Average	34.8		45.4		19.8		-	-
Total							1,842	619

Notes: The total record for each paradigm is the result of the sum of the quotes labelled with second-level codes (for instance, 1.1) and those labelled with the more general paradigm label (for instance, 1); $A = B / G \times 100$; $C = D / G \times 100$; $E = F / G \times 100$.

Source: Authors' elaboration.

On average, the quotes labelled with the security paradigm are now at 19.8% of the total coded text, up from 11.7% in the early 2000s. This increase in the reference to security matters in strategic aid documents comes at the expense of the social development paradigm, which lowers its profile, from 47.2% of total quotes to 34.8% (although clearly remaining relevant). As for the sustainable development paradigm, its weight is significant in both periods, with a slight increase of 4.3 percentage points from the first to the second period.

Therefore, all three paradigms – social development, sustainable development, and security – coexist in the development narrative; a feature consistent with the fact that aid can be multi-purpose. What has changed from one period to the next is the weight of those three groups of elements in terms of the aid discourse. This coexistence is evident in both time and space, with the only exception of France in the first period. For the rest of the donors, all paradigms show a prevalence of at least 9.7% (the weight of the security paradigm in Germany's strategic plan for the first period) and no greater than 69.2% (the weight of the sustainable development agenda in Spain's strategic plan for the second period).

In the first period, the Netherlands stand out for a strongly securitized narrative (23.5% of total references to objectives of aid). EU institutions, the UK and Sweden follow with around 12-13% of total quotes; then Germany and Spain with a slightly lower share. As mentioned before, France records no references to security in its aid narrative during this first period. Countries follow a similar grouping in the second period. The Netherlands records a similar share of references to security as an aid objective, while the rest of the countries (with the exception of the UK) highlight security goals in a similar fashion (between 14.6% and 18.4%).

One relevant change between the first and the second period is that of the UK, whose share of references to security jumps from 9.7% to 34.9%. Also, France, with no references to security in

the first period, has now joined the general group with 18.4% of total coded paragraphs. These two changes are responsible for the general securitization of the EU narrative on aid.

Motives for aid are here found to represent only a minor part of the strategic discourse of EU donors. Only 201 quotes refer to the motives of aid, *versus* 4,139 on aid objectives (Table 7). The distribution of these quotes across periods and donors yields very interesting results linked to the whole aid securitization debate. There is an increase in the overall number of references to the motives of aid: 92 in the first period *versus* 109 in the second. Therefore, it would seem that political events in Europe during the 2010s call for clear justifications on the part of donors (regarding why public funds should be channelled for development purposes). This increase responds almost entirely to a significant increase in references to selfish motives and arguments of self-help and self-interest on the part of the Netherlands (from 3 to 15) and the UK (from 2 to 30), while the rest of the countries have maintained or reduced this sort of argument in their aid narrative.

In the case of the UK, but not of the Netherlands, this greater emphasis comes hand in hand with a more securitized narrative. France, which records an increased number of references to security, still has no mentions to selfish aid motives in the second period. In short, maybe counterintuitively, there is not a clear correspondence between securitization of aid and donors' self-interest. Notably, references to national interests need not be limited to matters of security and defence. In fact, the Dutch strategy argues mainly for commercial interests: "These developments call for a new aid, trade, and investment agenda. At international level, we are pursuing three important aims. First, to eradicate extreme poverty ('getting to zero') in a single generation; second, sustainable, inclusive growth all over the world; and third, success for Dutch companies abroad" (MFA, 2013).

Table 7. Motives of aid in EU MS discourses (number of quotes by code)

1st period	Solidarity / Moral obligation / Responsibility	Common efforts / Common goods / Common interests / Global Public Goods	Self-help/Self-Interest	Total
EU inst.	3	3	0	6
Netherlands	4	3	3	10
UK	3	14	2	19
Germany	2	3	2	7
France	4	0	0	4
Sweden	9	20	1	30
Spain	4	7	5	16
Total	29	50	13	92
2nd period	Solidarity / Moral obligation / Responsibility	Common efforts / Common goods / Common interests / Global Public Goods	Self-help/Self-Interest	Total
EU inst.	2	2	1	5
Netherlands	3	9	15	27
UK	6	4	30	40
Germany	0	12	0	12
France	1	2	0	3
Sweden	1	4	0	5

Spain	4	12	1	17
Total	17	45	47	109

Source: Authors' elaboration.

The *de facto* securitization of aid

As already mentioned, in order to assess the *de facto* securitization of EU aid, changes in aid allocation to the security sector must be explored. Once the adjustments related to the EU-Africa Trust Fund are integrated into the total EU aid, an increase of the 'conflict, peace and security' sector is confirmed for the years following the refugee crisis and the Valletta Summit (Figure 1). In 2016 and 2017, the EU institutions have allocated to this sector an average of USD 755 million per year in 2018 constant prices, while between 2008 and 2015 the average was USD 530 million. This represented an increase of 26%. Similarly, MS have increased the volume of aid allocated to the security sector by 55%, going from a yearly average of 1,043 million US dollars between 2008 and 2015 to 1,579 million US dollars in 2016 and 2017. This shift was mainly driven by Germany and the UK, with increases of 76% and 96%.

Figure 1. ODA for the 'conflicts, peace and security' sector, EU institutions and main MS (millions of 2018 US dollars)

Source: OECD CRS (Data extracted on 10 Mar 2021), EU (2019) and authors' calculations

That said, from a longer-term perspective, the securitization trend in the EU institutions is not so clear, as a similar or even higher volume of ODA was allocated to the security sector in 2009,

2011 and 2014. On the contrary, Germany and the UK are at their highest level of securitization in absolute terms, taking a ten-year perspective. In percentage terms, securitization trends in Europe must be further relativized. The security sector takes a very small portion of aid (Figure 2). The Netherlands and the UK have indeed increased such percentage, the former going from a yearly average of 3.72% before the refugee crisis to 4.52% afterwards, and the latter going from 3.58% to 5.05%. However, in the rest of the counties analysed, this ratio has followed a negative trend, and in the case of the European Commission, it has stabilized around a relatively low percentage of 3.5%, a level already reached in certain years prior to the Valetta summit and the so-called refugee crisis.

Figure 2. Share of bilateral aid allocated to the ‘conflicts, peace and security’ (As % of aid allocated to security, peace and conflict over total aid in millions of 2018 US dollars)

Source: CRS-OECD (Data extracted on 10 Mar 2021), EU (2019) and authors’ calculations

Conclusion

This work analyses aid securitization in the EU from two distinct angles: that of the securitization of the aid discourse and its eventual reflection in the sector allocation of aid flows. Selecting, for each of the seven donors analysed, two documents representing their views in two different moments in time has allowed for the observation of the securitization process across a decade and a half; a period characterized by the effects of the Great Recession and the so-called refugee crisis.¹⁰

Although the European Consensuses on Development (texts that gather and balance the distinct political views on aid of all EU MS, as well as of the EU institutions) do not reveal a clear securitization of aid, some individual strategic documents from the key European donors clearly do. This is the case for the UK and France. It could be argued that the Netherlands has also gone through a securitization of its aid narrative. However, such securitization was already evident in its strategic document from the first period. Therefore, either its aid discourse was always securitized, or such securitization happened before the time frame under study in this research.

As for the allocation of aid flows, although the evolution of ‘securitized aid’ in absolute terms records an increase, which is mostly due to commitments on the part of Germany and the UK,

the proportion of such aid with respect to total aid allocated has hardly varied, on average, for this selection of donors. It should be noted, however, that the Netherlands and the UK have indeed increased such percentage and reached a maximum of 5%.

In short, there is not a perfect match between self-interest as the key motive for aid, a securitization of the aid discourse, and increasing funds for security purposes. Indeed, the only donor where this match happens is the UK. In the case of the Netherlands, although the aid discourse was already securitized in the first period, it made the case for aid on the grounds of self-interest more strongly in the second period, while aid flows for security purposes increased. Despite an obvious securitization of the French aid discourse, selfish arguments are not more strongly emphasized now than in the early 2000s, and securitized aid flows stand at low levels.

Aid arguments need not be exclusive, even when very different. Social and sustainable development, security, self-interest, and solidarity can all coexist in aid narratives. Indeed, they actually do. What appears to have changed between the early 2000s and the present is that different emphases have been given to different paradigms and motives.

This raises the interesting question of who these documents are written for; an issue that relates to one (underexplored) element of the theory of securitization which is the audience and its interaction with the elites. Clearly, the design processes of the diverse documents under review and the political debates around them might be very different. While the EU Consensus on Development have been debated internationally, among peer nations, individual strategies might conceivably be negotiated with (and written for) domestic political stakeholders. In that regard, important shifts in the aid narratives of certain donors might be linked to changes in governing parties or administrations, as well as to changing social, economic, and political climates at the national level. For instance, the UK's stronger emphasis on self-interest and security coincides with the conservative turn in the governing party and the Brexit campaign (Olivié and Pérez, 2020).

In this sense, it is important to note that the case for aid and, more specifically, aid as a way to fulfil one's interests, is more clearly made by donors with high and/or increasing aid budgets (in relation to the size of their economy), a strong involvement in the peace and security sector and domestic shifts towards more conservative governments. In that same line, Spain, who has cut its aid budget by three quarters in ten years, according to OECD data, might be interpreting that it does not need to make the case for aid.

Biographical notes

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Annex

Aid activities by EU institutions and MS related to the EU Emergency Trust Fund by sector as per description of project title in CRS aid activity database (USD Million)

SectorName	Year	DonorName	ProjectTitle	Amount	
152. Conflict, Peace & Security	2017	Germany	EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa and International Organisation for Migration initiative	35.94	
	2017	United Kingdom	To work through the EU Emergency Trust Fund to promote stability in three regions of Africa and enable better migration management.	0.18	
	2017	Germany	European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa - Managing of mixed migration flows	119.81	
	2017	Germany	European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF) - Technical Facility	3.59	
			Subtotal 152. Conflict. Peace & Security	159.53	32%
130. Population Policies/Programmes & Reproductive Health	2017	EU Institutions	Contribution from the GPGC Migration and Asylum to the Emergency Trust Fund for Africa	17.93	
	2016	EU Institutions	Contribution from the GPGC Migration and Asylum to the Emergency Trust Fund for Africa	12.07	
			Subtotal 130. Population Policies/Programmes & Reproductive Health	30.00	6%
151. Government & Civil Society-general	2017	EU Institutions	Second contribution from the PanAf programme to the African Emergency Trust Fund.	18.05	
	2017	United Kingdom	2To work through the EU Emergency Trust Fund to promote stability in three regions of Africa and enable better migration management.	0.36	
	2016	United Kingdom	UK contribution to the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for stability and addressing root causes of irregular migration and displaced persons	0.70	
			Subtotal 151 Government & Civil Society-general	19.11	4%
160. Other Social Infrastructure & Services	2016	Germany	German contribution to the EU Trust Fund	3.63	
			Subtotal 160. Other Social Infrastructure & Services	3.63	
410. General Environment Protection	2017	EU Institutions	Audit financier du projet FED/2011/262-037	0.13	
			Subtotal 410. General Environment Protection	0.13	

SectorName	Year	DonorName	ProjectTitle	Amount	
430. Other Multisector	2017	EU Institutions	Contribution to the EU Trust Fund for Africa, Sahel Lake Chad Window from the Pro-Resilience Actions 2016	11.95	
	2017	EU Institutions	European Emergency Trust Fund for stability and addressing root causes of irregular migration and displaced persons in Africa- South Sudan	103.28	
	2016	EU Institutions	Contribution from the PanAf programme to the African Emergency Trust Fund.	11.95	
	2016	EU Institutions	Contribution to the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for stability and addressing root causes of irregular migration and displaced persons	12.07	
	2016	EU Institutions	Contribution to the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for stability and addressing root causes of irregular migration and displaced persons	60.35	
	2016	EU Institutions	Contribution to the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for stability and addressing root causes of irregular migration and displaced persons	36.21	
	2016	EU Institutions	Contribution to the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for stability and addressing root causes of irregular migration and displaced persons	46.49	
				Subtotal 430. Other Multisector	282.30
720. Emergency Response	2017	United Kingdom	To work through the EU Emergency Trust Fund to promote stability in three regions of Africa and enable better migration management.	0.18	
			Subtotal 72. Emergency Response	0.18	0%
Total EU Emergency Trust Fund in CRS				494.87	

Source: CRS-OECD

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³ For instance, when compared with OLIVIE, I. & PÉREZ, A. 2019. Solidarity and security in the EU discourse on aid. In: OLIVIE, I. & PÉREZ, A. (eds.) *Aid power and politics*. Oxford: Routledge., this article deepens into the analysis in two ways. On the one hand, it adds two donors to the sample of the EU community explored. Not only does this allow for a greater representativity of the EU as a donor, but it also includes different donor profiles by including a Nordic country as well as a donor from the South. On the other hand, the analysis of securitization is expanded by including that of ODA flows as well.

⁴ This analysis covers pre-Brexit aid narratives and flows. Therefore, the UK is still considered part of the EU.

⁵ This ranking, as well as that of Table 1, reflects total net ODA disbursements by MS and therefore duplicates funds channelled via EU institutions. We consider that this does not pose a methodological problem. Much to the contrary, it better captures major donors in the European development community, which is the goal of this exercise.

⁶ <https://www.oecd.org/dac/oecd-development-co-operation-peer-reviews-european-union-2018-9789264309494-en.htm>

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<http://www.exteriores.gob.es/portal/es/saladeprensa/multimedia/publicaciones/paginas/cooperacion/planificacion.aspx>

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/international-partnerships/european-development-policy_en

⁹ Both Brown, Grävingholt, and Raddatz BROWN, S., GRÄVINGHOLT, J. & RADDATZ, R. 2016. The Securitization of Foreign Aid: Trends, Explanations and Prospects. In: BROWN, S. & GRÄVINGHOLT, J. (eds.) *The Securitization of Foreign Aid*. London: Palgrave Macmillan. and FURNESS, M. & GÄNZLE, S. Ibid. The European Union’s Development Policy: A Balancing Act between ‘a More Comprehensive Approach’ and ‘Creeping Securitisation’. In: BROWN, S. & GRÄVINGHOLT, J. (eds.). associate the ‘whole-of-government approach’ with a discourse of securitized aid. However, it could be argued that this concept, linked to the agenda on policy coherence for development, might be reflecting a sense of coherent external action towards a single set of goals that could be aligned with any of the three paradigms (and not exclusively with the third). Therefore, we have not included this concept in our list of codes.

¹⁰ It should be noted that not all documents (for each period) are dated the same year. This could limit the comparability of documents although this issue is related with the planning cycles of different donors.